

Supporting Information

Exploring the prime site in caspases as a novel chemical strategy for understanding the mechanisms of cell death: a proof of concept study on necroptosis in cancer cells

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Table 1 K_i parameters of inhibitors from zVAD-Bzl-X library measured for mouse and human pro-inflammatory caspases. Inhibition constants were calculated based on Morrison equation, and the results are presented as averages from at least three independent measurements (SD for all inhibitors is below 15%).

Inhibitor/Caspase	mCasp-1	mCasp-11	hCasp-1	hCasp-4	hCasp-5
zVAD-bzl	0.623	57.9	3.71	24.8	14.7
zVAD-isophtalic-X-NH₂					
Ala	0.961	124	5.11	47.6	27.4
Arg	4.37	403	12.0	139	116
Asn	0.611	107	2.11	47.2	16.1
Gln	0.210	85.3	2.87	36.1	19.8
Glu	0.510	109	2.82	50.2	18.5
Gly	2.32	252	9.35	96.8	44.5
His	0.401	136	2.62	54.4	27.2
Ile	0.652	281	5.53	52.8	40.9
Leu	0.462	123	6.54	32.8	20.8
Lys	0.702	149	2.82	60.4	65.6
Nle	0.631	203	4.14	76.2	33.4
Phe	0.401	79.2	1.16	26.3	2.4
Pro	0.977	165	3.92	50.3	71.4
Ser	0.332	97.1	1.99	37.7	19.1
Thr	0.579	182	2.96	55.4	30.1
Trp	0.838	77.9	0.79	35.8	2.3
Tyr	0.297	113	1.32	42.5	15.3
Val	0.396	216	4.54	67.1	60.9
Met	0.412	208	4.51	73.2	59.7
zVAD-terephtalic-X-NH₂					
Ala	0.624	27.2	4.54	15.1	16.1
Arg	0.591	15.6	7.51	7.05	11.2
Asn	0.178	7.42	3.54	3.12	7.91
Gln	0.342	7.05	3.84	5.54	5.92
Glu	0.317	6.31	3.21	6.22	6.14
Gly	0.726	20.8	6.68	24.3	26.3
His	0.406	15.7	4.83	6.61	13.4
Ile	0.871	33.6	7.55	6.72	13.3
Leu	0.926	24.3	8.43	4.64	9.32
Lys	0.591	9.14	6.89	7.33	13.8
Nle	1.72	40.2	8.62	20.8	25.6
Phe	0.767	9.32	4.33	7.42	6.22
Pro	1.54	55.2	4.41	35.1	63.4
Ser	0.805	13.8	4.05	16.2	13.7
Thr	1.44	34.9	5.78	20.2	20.6
Trp	1.37	4.94	5.21	8.44	3.21
Tyr	0.433	4.81	4.54	2.61	3.52
Val	1.09	16.7	5.34	5.62	11.0
Met	0.508	9.05	6.25	7.83	15.3

Table 2 K_i parameters of inhibitors from zVAD-Bzl-X library measured for human apoptotic caspases. Inhibition constants were calculated based on Morrison equation, and the results are presented as averages from at least three independent measurements (SD for all inhibitors is below 15%).

Inhibitor/Caspase	hCasp-3	hCasp-7	hCasp-8	hCasp-9	hCasp-10
zVAD-bzl	1110	740	2.55	10.2	17.1
zVAD-isophtalic-X-NH₂					
Ala	1929	846	9.03	6.39	54.1
Arg	3702	1034	44.2	29.4	70.2
Asn	2028	891	19.1	7.14	30.1
Gln	1643	677	11.2	7.58	24.4
Glu	2786	1782	13.2	18.2	31.9
Gly	3335	1762	13.7	25.7	77.8
His	1601	662	15.3	5.41	21.2
Ile	2410	478	41.6	4.03	32.2
Leu	1806	599	31.9	9.71	16.8
Lys	1548	671	14.2	9.01	20.5
Nle	1038	395	19.8	10.9	30.2
Phe	295	233	15.2	13.4	31.3
Pro	1031	284	15.6	9.27	32.4
Ser	1010	715	11.5	8.88	29.1
Thr	792	859	15.0	11.5	36.8
Trp	388	675	1.83	17.4	35.3
Tyr	888	1046	9.51	6.91	27.1
Val	2810	519	33.3	3.32	37.9
Met	527	302	27.8	4.35	39.1
zVAD-terephtalic-X-NH₂					
Ala	1983	1430	33.4	2.36	8.22
Arg	1396	603	29.5	4.02	3.62
Asn	2255	687	28.9	1.94	3.05
Gln	3240	1064	42.3	3.04	5.12
Glu	3635	860	41.7	1.25	5.06
Gly	2218	557	13.2	1.91	13.1
His	3192	883	40.8	1.99	4.84
Ile	974	1628	135	14.8	7.66
Leu	1760	1313	120	12.7	4.74
Lys	1873	621	37.2	4.62	3.52
Nle	845	1348	112	14.4	12.6
Phe	1212	1423	149	11.6	8.84
Pro	1514	1521	12.4	7.71	5.71
Ser	1315	900	11.9	1.13	9.12
Thr	1524	1307	26.6	3.43	7.52
Trp	1236	1372	88.1	8.85	5.43
Tyr	1421	1436	59.1	8.22	1.63
Val	1827	1692	46.7	8.14	4.54
Met	456	1409	63.6	4.95	3.40

Table 3. Structures of synthesized bifunctional caspase inhibitors.

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Nle-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Phe-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Pro-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Ser-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Thr-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Trp-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Tyr-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophthalic-Ala-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-terephthalic-Met-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophthalic-Ala-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Arg-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Asn-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Glu-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Gln-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Gly-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-His-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Ile-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Leu-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Lys-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-isophtalic-Nle-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Phe-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Pro-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Ser-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Thr-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Trp-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Tyr-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Val-NH₂

Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp-*isophtalic*-Met-NH₂

Table 4. Molecular masses of synthesized inhibitors used in this study. All of inhibitors displayed at least 97% purity.

No.	Inhibitor structure	[M+H] ⁺ / [M+Na ⁺] calculated	[M+H] ⁺ / [M+Na ⁺] measured
1	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Ala-NH ₂	692.2544	692.2534
2	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Arg-NH ₂	755.3286	755.3239
3	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Asn-NH ₂	735.2602	735.2611
4	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Glu-NH ₂	750.2599	750.2609
5	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Gln-NH ₂	749.2758	749.2753
6	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Gly-NH ₂	678.2387	678.2388
7	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -His-NH ₂	736.2864	736.2953
8	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Ile-NH ₂	734.3013	734.3015
9	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Leu-NH ₂	734.3013	734.3017
10	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Lys-NH ₂	727.3225	727.3309
11	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Nle-NH ₂	734.3013	734.3023
12	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Phe-NH ₂	768.2857	768.2849
13	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Pro-NH ₂	718.2700	718.2687
14	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Ser-NH ₂	708.2493	708.2498
15	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Thr-NH ₂	700.2952	700.2809
16	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Trp-NH ₂	807.2966	807.2962
17	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Tyr-NH ₂	784.2806	784.2800
18	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Val-NH ₂	720.2857	720.2856
19	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>isophtalic</i> -Met-NH ₂	752.2577	752.2571
20	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Ala-NH ₂	670.2646	670.2701
21	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Arg-NH ₂	755.3286	755.3412
22	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Asn-NH ₂	713.2704	713.2758
23	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Glu-NH ₂	728.2701	728.2791
24	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Gln-NH ₂	728.2861	728.2791
25	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Gly-NH ₂	656.2490	656.2557
26	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -His-NH ₂	735.2864	736.2973
27	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Ile-NH ₂	711.3116	712.3196
28	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Leu-NH ₂	712.3116	712.3198
29	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Lys-NH ₂	727.3225	727.3295
30	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Nle-NH ₂	734.3013	734.2997
31	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Phe-NH ₂	768.2857	768.2861
32	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Pro-NH ₂	718.2700	718.2714
33	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Ser-NH ₂	708.2493	708.2499
34	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Thr-NH ₂	722.2649	722.2648
35	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Trp-NH ₂	807.2964	807.2966
36	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Tyr-NH ₂	784.2806	784.2805
37	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Val-NH ₂	720.2857	720.2856
38	Cbz-Val-Ala-Asp- <i>terephthalic</i> -Met-NH ₂	752.2577	752.2578

Figure 1 Two possible ways of caspases inactivation – reversible and irreversible. For k_{obs} calculation a Kitz-Wilson equation (JBC, 1962) was used.

Figure 2 The correlation between inhibition parameters (K_I) for human pro-inflammatory caspases. **Panel A** Correlation between K_I parameters for caspase-1 and caspase-4. These enzymes display good correlation for *iso*-Bzl inhibitors (similar specificity) and no correlation for *tere*-Bzl inhibitors (different specificity). **Panel B** Correlation between K_I parameters for caspase-1 and caspase-5. These enzymes display good correlation for *iso*-Bzl inhibitors (similar specificity) and no correlation for *tere*-Bzl inhibitors (different specificity). **Panel C** Correlation between K_I parameters for caspase-4 and caspase-5. These enzymes display good correlation for both *iso*-Bzl and *tere*-Bzl demonstrating that their prime site architecture is similar. Correlation was expressed as Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) calculated in Graph Pad Prism 7.0 software.

Figure 3 The correlation between inhibition parameters (K_I) for selected human apoptotic caspases. **Panel A** Correlation between K_I parameters for caspase-3 and caspase-7. These enzymes display only moderate correlation for *iso*-Bzl inhibitors and almost no correlation for *tere*-Bzl inhibitors, demonstrating that the specificity in the prime region of these closely related enzyme is different. **Panel B** Correlation between K_I parameters for closely related caspase-10 and caspase-8. These enzymes display no correlation for either *iso*-Bzl or *tere*-Bzl inhibitors. Correlation was expressed as Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) calculated in Graph Pad Prism 7.0 software.

A

Figure 4 Dissecting necroptosis with caspase inhibitors. **Panel A** HT-29 cells were preincubated with selected inhibitors, followed by induction of apoptosis or necroptosis. zVAD-fmk, a potent, broad spectrum caspases inhibitor can rescue cells from apoptosis but not necroptosis. However, when cells were pretreated with both zVAD-fmk and Nec-1, both processes were inhibited. The use of caspase-8 and caspase-8-FLIP (zVAD-Bzl-X) either caspase-10 (zVAD-AOMK-X) selective inhibitors demonstrate that caspase-8 (or caspase-8-FLIP) but not caspase-10 is involved in necroptosis in HT-29 cells. **Panel B** HT-29 cells were preincubated with selected inhibitors, followed by induction of apoptosis (TNF- α + Birinapant) or necroptosis (TNF- α + Birinapant + Nec-1). The use of panel of caspase-8 and caspase-10 selective inhibitors in combination with TNF- α +Birinapant stimulants demonstrate that this necroptotic pathway is also driven by caspase-8 (caspase-8/FLIP), and caspase-10 does not contribute to this type of cell death.

Figure 5. To dissect the inhibition mode of caspase-8 and caspase-10 we performed analysis of inhibition curves, and adjusted them to either Morisson equation (reversible inhibition) or Kitz-Wilson equation (irreversible inhibition). Only zVAD-AOMK shows irreversible inhibition towards caspase-10. zVAD-Bzl and zVAD-AOMK act in reversible fashion with caspase-8 at early timeframe of the reaction, but after prolonged incubation the inhibitor-enzyme complex matures and some portion of enzyme is covalently modified with slow kinetics.

Figure 6. FLIP_L forms a heterodimer with caspase-8, and it is this form of caspase-8 that blocks the necroptosis pathway. Catalytically active caspase-8:FLIP_L complex was assembled to verify whether the specificity of inhibitors will remain the same.

2. ZVAD-iso-R-NH2 con 150

8226_2016_A1 64 (1.075) Cm (61:64)

TOF MS ES+
2.07e3

5. ZVAD-iso-E-NH2 con 150
8229_2016_A2 139 (2.354) Cm (136:140)

TOF MS ES+
4.52e3

6. ZVAD-iso-Q-NH2 con 150
8230_2016_A2 20 (0.324) Cm (19:22)

TOF MS ES+
1.79e3

8. ZVAD-isdo-H-NH2 con 150
8232_2016_A2 6 (0.085) Cm (6:8)

TOF MS ES+
1.33e3

10. ZVAD-isdo-L-NH2 con 150
8234_2016_A1 114 (1.929) Cm (113:114)

TOF MS ES+
1.51e3

11. ZVAD-isdo-K-NH2 con 150
8235_2016_A1 30 (0.495) Cm (29:30)

TOF MS ES+
1.35e3

12. ZVAD-isdo-Nle-NH2 con 150
8236_2016_A2 39 (0.648)

TOF MS ES+
1.32e3

13. ZVAD-isdo-F-NH2 con 150
8237_2016_A1 24 (0.393)

TOF MS ES+
1.69e3

15. ZVAD-isdo-S-NH2 con 150
8239_2016_A1 72 (1.213) Cm (70:72)

TOF MS ES+
1.15e3

17. ZVAD-iso-W-NH2 con 150
8241_2016_A2 39 (0.647) Cm (35:39)

TOF MS ES+
4.87e3

20. ZVAD-isdo-M-NH2 con 150
8244_2016_A2 8 (0.120) Cm (6:8)

TOF MS ES+
2.01e3

07-11-2017
tere_Ala_2 218 (3.703) Cm (218-(200:209+234:242))

TOF MSMS 670.00ES+
3.27e6

07-11-2017
tere_ARG 174 (2.959) Cm (172:176)

TOF MSMS 755.00ES+
1.96e7

4-1-2018
ZVAD-TERE-ASN 704 (2.739)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.32e5

07-11-2017

tere_GLU 212 (3.601) Cm (212-(141:189+250.268))

TOF MSMS 728.00ES+
8.21e5

07-11-2017
tere_q 213 (3.618) Cm (213)

TOF MSMS 727.00ES+
1.31e6

07-11-2017
tere_GLY 214 (3.635) Cm (214-(189:196+240:245))

TOF MSMS 656.00ES+
8.79e5

07-11-2017
tere_HIS 172 (2.925) Cm (170:173-(121:144+220:255))

TOF MSMS 736.00ES+
1.33e7

07-11-2017
Iere_ILE 232 (3.939) Cm (231:232)

TOF MSMS 712.00ES+
7.40e3

07-11-2017
tere_LEU 252 (4.278)

TOF MSMS 712.00ES+
3.10e4

Figure 8. m/z analysis and analytical HPLC analysis of all caspase inhibitors used in this study.

